

DETERMINATION AND ANALYSIS OF THE MECHANICAL DAMAGE DEGREE OF COTTONSEED RESULTING FROM THE LINTING PROCESS

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Abstract. This article addresses the issue of determining and analyzing the degree of mechanical damage to cottonseed resulting from the linting process. The study investigates the levels of seed damage under various rotational speeds and operating modes. Based on statistical and technological analysis, optimal operating conditions are developed. In addition, the main structural and technological factors influencing the degree of damage are identified, and recommendations are provided to improve the efficiency of linter machines.

Keywords: linter machine, frequency converter, saw cylinder, electric motor, technological process, automation, product quality, mechanical damage, linear speed.

Introduction. In seed cotton processing enterprises, the technological stages such as conveying, drying, removal of impurities, fiber separation from seed cotton, lint removal from seed, seed cleaning, grading, treatment, packaging, storage, and transportation are carried out using equipment in accordance with established standards [1].

Materials and Methods. Currently, conventional linter machines widely used in the cotton industry - especially the constant-speed operation of their saw cylinders and beaters - are observed to cause significant mechanical damage to seed cotton. This results in various types of seed damage, including hull cracking, kernel exposure, crushing, and deformation (Figure 1). Consequently, the germination capacity of the

seed decreases, an excessive amount of seed hull fragments is detected in the final product, and the quality indicators of the lint deteriorate [2].

The main cause of these issues is the mismatch between the linear velocities of the saw cylinder and the beater within the working chamber of the linter machine, as well as the lack of automatic adjustment according to different cotton varieties or seed conditions.

Figure 1. Visual appearance of damaged cottonseeds

- a) Surface cracks b) Surface pits d) Surface damage
- e) Deformations f) Cracks / Fractures

Figure 2. Newly Designed Linter Machine with Automatic Control System

In our study, the proposed technological solution allows for the separate and precise control of the rotational speeds of the saw cylinder and the beater using frequency converters. This makes it possible to coordinate the linear velocities of both working units, maintaining the optimal speed ratio (V_1/V_2) between the saw cylinder and the beater [3]. This is a critical factor, as the mismatch in their speeds is one of the main causes of seed crushing, hull cracking, and kernel damage.

To determine the mechanical damage to cottonseed under different rotational speeds of the saw cylinder and beater, experimental tests were conducted using a 5LP-160 linter machine installed in the linting section of the main building at the cotton processing plant belonging to “NT Chust G‘alla Cluster” LLC (Figure 1). The tests were carried out on Namangan-34 variety, R-1 generation, hand-picked cotton with a moisture content of 7.8% and impurity level of 3.0%.

Results and Discussion. From the linter machine output, two working samples of 50 grams each were collected. The samples were placed in a glass container and treated with 20–30 ml of sulfuric acid with a density of 1.84 g/cm³. After mixing for approximately 10 minutes to completely remove the lint, the samples were thoroughly rinsed and dried using filter paper (Figure 2).

The degree of mechanical damage to the cottonseed was determined through visual inspection in accordance with Uzbek Standard O‘z DSt 603-2020 and GOST 13056.7-81. In each experimental replication, 200 cottonseeds were selected and examined under a microscope to assess their damage.

Figure 3. Samples Collected for the Experiment

The degree of mechanical damage to cottonseed was determined using the following formula [4]:

$$M_{\text{damage}} = \frac{C * 100}{W + C}$$

Where:

C – number of undamaged whole seeds

W – number of damaged seeds

Table 1.

Mechanical Damage Rates of Cottonseed Based on Experimental Results

№	Conducted Experiments	Mechanical Damage to Cottonseed
1	Total number of seeds: 200 Number of damaged seeds: 6	$M_{\text{damage}} = \frac{C \cdot 100}{W + C} = \frac{6 \cdot 100}{200} = 3 \%$
2	Total number of seeds: 200 Number of damaged seeds: 4	$M_{\text{damage}} = \frac{C \cdot 100}{W + C} = \frac{4 \cdot 100}{200} = 2 \%$
3	Total number of seeds: 200 Number of damaged seeds: 8	$M_{\text{damage}} = \frac{C \cdot 100}{W + C} = \frac{8 \cdot 100}{200} = 4 \%$

Average Mechanical Damage Percentage:

$$\text{Average} = \frac{2\% + 3\% + 4\%}{3} = 3\%$$

According to the results of three repeated experiments, samples of 200 cottonseeds were taken and analyzed each time. The number of damaged seeds was 4, 6, and 8 respectively, which corresponds to 2%, 3%, and 4%. The average level of mechanical damage based on these experimental results was exactly 3% (Tab 1).

Conclusion. Based on the conducted research, the level of mechanical damage to the cottonseeds exiting the linter machine was analyzed under laboratory conditions. The condition of seed damage was studied under various design parameters and operating modes, and their impact on technological indicators was evaluated. Experimental tests showed that in existing conventional machines, the level of seed damage is relatively high, which negatively affects their quality as planting material.

In contrast, in the linter machine modernized based on the proposed new technological solution, the rotational speeds of the saw cylinder and the beater were controlled using frequency converters. This allowed for the optimization of the mechanical forces acting on the seeds. The test results demonstrated that the level of damage to cottonseeds was significantly reduced when using the upgraded equipment.

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